

A Hospital-Based Study Assessing Serum Magnesium Levels and its Correlation with Glycemic Status in Type II Diabetes Patients: An Analytical Study

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Abstract

Aim: The aim of the present study was to assess the level of serum magnesium in diagnosed Type II diabetics without microvascular and macrovascular complications and correlate with glycemic status.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Biochemistry. The data was collected for finding out correlation between the glycemic index and serum magnesium was analysed and the results were obtained. The estimated sample size was 50. The sampling type was purposive sample.

Results: 32 (64%) were in the age group of 41–60 years, 10 (20%) were in age group of 19–40 years, whereas 8 (16%) were between 61 and 80 years. 32 (64%) were male and 18 (36%) were female. Thus, there was male preponderance. 24 (48%) were diabetic since 11–20 years, 15 (30%) were diabetic since 0–10 years, 8 (16%) were diabetic since 21–30 years, while 3 (6%) were diabetic since >30 years. Laboratory reports revealed that there was significant difference in mean total leukocyte count, Serum glutamic pyruvic transaminase (SGPT), serum glutamic-oxaloacetic transaminase (SGOT), K⁺, Randon blood sugar (RBS), and HbA1c between hypomagnesemia patients compared to normomagnesemia patients ($P < 0.05$) There was no significant difference in other laboratory values between the two groups. The prevalence of hypomagnesemia in patient with HbA1c <7% was 20% as compared to that of normomagnesemia (60%), while the prevalence of hypomagnesemia in patient with HbA1c >7% was 80% as compared to that of normomagnesemia (40%). This difference of S. Mg level in relation to HbA1c was statistically highly significant.

Conclusion: The study concluded that that low S. Mg level in type 2 diabetes patients may be associated with higher HbA1c level, higher incidence of retinopathy and nephropathy. Routine monitoring and correcting S. Mg levels in type 2 diabetes patients may help in better control of HbA1c and delaying progression to retinopathy and nephropathy.

Keywords: Magnesium, HbA1c, Diabetes.

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Introduction

Type 2 diabetes makes 90% of diabetes cases. [1] Its worldwide prevalence may be 439 million by 2030. [2] According to the International Diabetes Federation and WHO, its prevalence is 10% [3] and over 19% of world's diabetics are Indians. [4] Magnesium is an essential mineral found in dietary fibers, non-starchy vegetables, fruits, nuts, and dairy products. [5] Hypomagnesemia has been reported in 25%–38% of type 2 diabetics [6] and to be associated with increased morbidity and mortality. [7,8]

In spite of innovative methods in the management of diabetes mellitus, the morbidity and mortality continue to be high.4 The deleterious effect of

diabetes in these patients is related to complications, including both macrovascular and microvascular complications. [5,6]

Diet is widely believed to play an important role in the development of type 2 diabetes (T2D) and the associated complications. [9,10] The glycated haemoglobin (HbA1c) is widely used for evaluation of diabetes control. [11] The HbA1c reveals the overall blood glucose levels over a period of 2-3 months, and the common use of the HbA1c assay is to assess changes in metabolic control that follow an alteration in treatment. [12] Magnesium (Mg) is one of the important components of many foods such as grains, nuts and

green leafy vegetables, and it plays a key role in many fundamental biological processes, including energy metabolism. Mg has received considerable attention for its potential role in improving insulin sensitivity and preventing diabetes and its cardiovascular complications. [13,14] It is claimed that Mg deficiency is common in diabetic patients and there is an inverse relationship between Mg intake and incidence of T2DM. [15]

Magnesium (Mg) is the fourth most abundant cation in the human body and plays a key role in many fundamental biological processes, including energy metabolism and DNA synthesis. It also plays an important role in the phosphorylation reactions of glucose and its metabolism. Its deficiency has been implicated in insulin resistance, carbohydrate intolerance, dyslipidemia, and complications of diabetes. [16] Mg has received considerable attention for its potential role in improving insulin sensitivity and preventing diabetes and its complications. However, results are inconsistent among the studies. [17,18] Observations in Caucasian diabetics have linked hypomagnesemia as being an additional risk factor for the development of diabetic retinopathy, but this correlation was not observed in black African diabetics. [17] Most of these studies could not be compared because of different methodology and inclusion and exclusion criteria.

The aim of the present study was to assess the level of serum magnesium in diagnosed Type II diabetics without microvascular and macrovascular complications and correlate with glycemic status.

Materials and Methods

A cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of Biochemistry, Netaji Subhas Medical College and Hospital, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India for eight months. The data was collected for finding out correlation between the glycemic index

and serum magnesium was analysed and the results were obtained. The estimated sample size was 50. The sampling type was purposive sample.

In sampling technique consecutive patients who were satisfying inclusion and exclusion criteria were included. Patients with type 2 DM of age 18 years and above, who gave written informed consent, were included in the study. The Exclusion criteria were the patients with chronic renal failure, Patients on diuretics. Patients receiving Magnesium supplements or Magnesium containing antacids, Malabsorption or chronic diarrhea, Patients with history of Epilepsy. The samples were processed for Serum Magnesium and HbA1C test by Immunoturbidimetric method on XL 640- Fully Automated Biochemistry Analyzer (Transasia Biomedical Ltd, India).

Detailed history was taken from the subjects and examination was done to diagnose micro vascular complications of diabetes. Laboratory investigations were done to support the findings of examination. All patients were examined for complete blood count, urine routine and for microalbuminuria, fasting blood glucose, post prandial blood glucose, hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c), blood urea, serum creatinine, S. Mg, ultrasonography abdomen, and fundus examination. Other examinations such as electrocardiography, 2D echocardiography, serum sodium, and potassium were done as per the indication.

Statistical analysis was done using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24.0, IBM. Pearson correlation coefficient was used to find correlation of S. Mg level with diabetic control. Odds ratio was calculated to find association of S. Mg level with DR and also to find association of S. Mg level with diabetic nephropathy.

Results

Table 1: Demographic data

Gender	N%
Male	32 (64)
Female	18 (36)
Age in years	
19-40 years	10 (20)
41-60 years	32 (64)
61-80 years	8 (16)
Duration of diabetes	
0-10 years	15 (30)
11-20 years	24 (48)
21-30 years	8 (16)
>30 years	3 (6)

32 (64%) were in the age group of 41–60 years, 10 (20%) were in age group of 19–40 years, whereas 8 (16%) were between 61 and 80 years. 32 (64%) were male and 18 (36%) were female. Thus, there was male preponderance. 24 (48%) were diabetic since 11–20 years, 15 (30%) were diabetic since 0–10 years, 8 (16%) were diabetic since 21–30 years, while 3 (6%) were diabetic since >30 years.

Table 2: Laboratory reports of the study population

Laboratory report	Mean±SD		P
	Normo-magneseemia	Hypo-magneseemia	
Hemoglobin	11.32±2.28	10.25±1.95	0.958
Total count	7544.86±2394.16	8428.16±2578.92	0.048
Platelets	2.03±0.88	2.11±0.89	0.576
Urea	35.85±17.52	43.07±25.75	0.55
Creatinine	1.24±0.92	1.52±1.38	0.155
SGPT	34.46±28.92	44.06±33.67	0.036
SGOT	32.28±20.46	46.44±28.62	0.001
Total bilirubin	1.12±0.86	1.21±0.66	0.412
Na+	135.35±3.77	135.75±2.86	0.432
K+	3.98±0.52	4.18±0.32	0.007
Cl-	99.25±3.05	98.42±1.68	0.088
RBG	228.92±62.06	258.82±70.65	0.007
HemoglobinA1C	7.23±1.20	8.72±1.56	<0.001

Laboratory reports revealed that there was significant difference in mean total leukocyte count, Serum glutamic pyruvic transaminase (SGPT), serum glutamic- oxaloacetic transaminase (SGOT), K+, Randon blood sugar (RBS), and HbA1c between hypomagneseemia patients compared to normomagneseemia patients (P < 0.05) There was no significant difference in other laboratory values between the two groups.

Table 3: Status of magnesium level according to hemoglobinA1c

	Normo magneseemic, n (%)	Hypomagneseemic, n (%)	p-value
Optimal (<7%)	36 (60)	8 (20)	<0.001
Uncontrolled (>7%)	24 (40)	32 (80)	
Total	60 (100)	40 (100)	

The prevalence of hypomagneseemia in patient with HbA1c <7% was 20% as compared to that of normomagneseemia (60%), while the prevalence of hypomagneseemia in patient with HbA1c >7% was 80% as compared to that of normomagneseemia (40%). This difference of S. Mg level in relation to HbA1c was statistically highly significant.

Table 4: Association of diabetic complications with serum magnesium levels

Magnesium (mg%)	PDR		NPDR		Nephropathy	
	Absent %	Present %	Absent %	Present %	Absent %	Present %
<1.8	18 (90)	1 (10)	8 (42.10)	11 (57.90)	15 (78.94)	4 (21.06)
>1.8	27 (87.09)	4 (12.90)	24 (77.41)	7 (22.59)	29 (93.54)	2 (6.46)
Total	45 (90)	5 (10)	32 (64)	18 (36)	43 (86)	7 (14)
OR	3.189		4.871		5.4	
P Value	0.068		0.001		0.001	

The incidence of PDR in hypomagneseemia patients was 10% as compared to 12.90% among patient having normal magnesium level. There was a statistically significant association between hypomagneseemia and Proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR). (P = 0.068; odds ratio [OR] = 3.189). Incidence of Non proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR) in hypomagneseemia patients was 57.90% as compared to 22.59% among patient having normal magnesium level. There was strong significant association between hypomagneseemia and NPDR (P = 0.001; OR = 4.871). Incidence of nephropathy in hypomagneseemia patients was 21.06% as compared to 6.46% among patient having normal magnesium level. There was strong significant association between hypomagneseemia and nephropathy (P = 0.001; OR = 5.4).

Discussion

Magnesium is an important and vital element in maintaining the body functions. It needs to be supplemented adequately. [19] Magnesium is the ninth most abundant element in the universe. [20,21] Magnesium is an essential element in biological systems. Magnesium typically known as the Mg²⁺ ion. It is an essential nutrient (i.e., element) for life and is present in every cell type in every organism. [22-25] Magnesium is the second most abundant intracellular cation in the body. It plays a significant role in many metabolic pathways, especially in glucose metabolism, by acting as a cofactor for several enzymes. It plays a vital role in insulin secretion, insulin binding and homeostasis. [26] Low levels of magnesium have shown to damage tyrosine kinase activity and receptors involved in signaling. [27] Both intracellular and extracellular magnesium deficits

are associated with type 2 diabetes mellitus. [28] Hypomagnesemia has been implicated in carbohydrate intolerance, hyperglycaemia, insulin resistance, complications of diabetes and hyperlipidemia. [29] Hypomagnesemia is common among diabetic patients which is frequently underdiagnosed.

32 (64%) were in the age group of 41–60 years, 10 (20%) were in age group of 19–40 years, whereas 8 (16%) were between 61 and 80 years. 32 (64%) were male and 18 (36%) were female. Thus, there was male preponderance. 24 (48%) were diabetic since 11–20 years, 15 (30%) were diabetic since 0–10 years, 8 (16%) were diabetic since 21–30 years, while 3 (6%) were diabetic since >30 years. Laboratory reports revealed that there was significant difference in mean total leukocyte count, Serum glutamic pyruvic transaminase (SGPT), serum glutamic-oxaloacetic transaminase (SGOT), K⁺, Random blood sugar (RBS), and HbA1c between hypomagnesemia patients compared to normomagnesemia patients ($P < 0.05$) There was no significant difference in other laboratory values between the two groups. The prevalence of hypomagnesemia in patient with HbA1c <7% was 20% as compared to that of normomagnesemia (60%), while the prevalence of hypomagnesemia in patient with HbA1c >7% was 80% as compared to that of normomagnesemia (40%). This difference of S. Mg level in relation to HbA1c was statistically highly significant. One study by Yossef HM et al [30] reported hypomagnesemia in almost 80% of their study population of type 2 DM patients. The high prevalence of hypomagnesemia in their study population may be because they had included patients with type 2 diabetes of at least 5 years' duration. Another study by Saeed et al [31] done in Iraq reported only 5% prevalence of hypomagnesemia in diabetics. This very low prevalence as compared to other studies may probably be due to race or dietary differences.

The incidence of PDR in hypomagnesemia patients was 10% as compared to 12.90% among patient having normal magnesium level. There was a statistically significant association between hypomagnesemia and Proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR). ($P = 0.068$; odds ratio [OR] = 3.189). Incidence of Non proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR) in hypomagnesemia patients was 57.90% as compared to 22.59% among patient having normal magnesium level. There was strong significant association between hypomagnesemia and NPDR ($P = 0.001$; OR = 4.871). Incidence of nephropathy in hypomagnesemia patients was 21.06% as compared to 6.46% among patient having normal magnesium level. There was strong significant association between hypomagnesemia and nephropathy ($P = 0.001$; OR = 5.4) which is

similar to study by Aksit et al [32] ($r = 0.332$, $P < 0.001$ respectively) and Yossef et al [31] ($r = 0.569$, $P < 0.0001$ respectively). In other studies, Wahid et al [33] and Kumar et al [34] reported significant difference in HbA1c values of diabetics with low and normal magnesium levels. [35] ($P < 0.0001$). Hence, there is a significant negative correlation of magnesium levels with HbA1c, however, the effect of Mg supplementation on glycemic control and bringing down HbA1c toward optimal remains to be seen which may be a topic for future research.

Conclusion

The study concluded that that low S. Mg level in type 2 diabetes patients may be associated with higher HbA1c level, higher incidence of retinopathy and nephropathy. Routine monitoring and correcting S. Mg levels in type 2 diabetes patients may help in better control of HbA1c and delaying progression to retinopathy and nephropathy. Furthermore, detailed analysis of the various parameters including dietary intake of magnesium, loss of magnesium owing to diuresis and malabsorption need to be considered while assessing serum magnesium levels in diabetic individuals and hence, call for detailed research in the area. Proper counseling should be given to diabetic patients about the need of taking magnesium through diet and the health care professionals should be made aware of the risks associated with hypomagnesemia left undiagnosed in diabetic patients and its ill effects.

References

1. González EM, Johansson S, Wallander MA, Rodríguez LG. Trends in the prevalence and incidence of diabetes in the UK: 1996–2005. *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health*. 2009 Apr 1;63(4):332-6.
2. Shaw JE, Sicree RA, Zimmet PZ. Global estimates of the prevalence of diabetes for 2010 and 2030. *Diabetes research and clinical practice*. 2010 Jan 1;87(1):4-14.
3. World Health Organization. *Global Report on Diabetes. Diabetes Country Profiles*. 2016. Geneva: WHO; 2016.
4. Nolan CJ, Damm P, Prentki M. Type 2 diabetes across generations: from pathophysiology to prevention and management. *The Lancet*. 2011 Jul 9;378(9786):169-81.
5. Dall TM, Narayan KV, Gillespie KB, Gallo PD, Blanchard TD, Solcan M, O'Grady M, Quick WW. Detecting type 2 diabetes and prediabetes among asymptomatic adults in the United States: modeling American Diabetes Association versus US Preventive Services Task Force diabetes screening guidelines. *Population health metrics*. 2014 Dec; 12:1-4.

6. de Lourdes Lima M, Cruz T, Pousada JC, Rodrigues LE, Barbosa K, Canguçu V. The effect of magnesium supplementation in increasing doses on the control of type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes care*. 1998 May 1;21(5):682-6.
7. Curiel-García JA, Rodríguez-Morán M, Guerrero-Romero F. Hypomagnesemia and mortality in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Magnesium research*. 2008 Sep 1;21(3):163-6.
8. Rodríguez-Morán M, Guerrero-Romero F. Low serum magnesium levels and foot ulcers in subjects with type 2 diabetes. *Archives of Medical Research*. 2001 Jul 1;32(4):300-3.
9. W, Lu J, Weng J, et al. Prevalence of diabetes among men and women in China. *N Engl J Med*. 2010;362(12):1090-1101.
10. Mangou A, Grammatikopoulou MG, Mirkopoulou D, Sailer N, Kotzamanidis C, Tsigga M. Associations between diet quality, health status and diabetic complications in patients with type 2 diabetes and comorbid obesity. *Endocrinol Nutr*. 2012;59(2): 109-116.
11. Saudek CD, Derr RL, Kalyani RR. Assessing glycemia in diabetes using self-monitoring blood glucose and hemoglobin A1c. *JAMA*. 2006;295(14):1688-1697.
12. Pfab T, Slowinski T, Godes M, Halle H, Priem F, Hocher B. Low birth weight, a risk factor for cardiovascular diseases in later life, is already associated with elevated fetal glycosylated hemoglobin at birth. *Circulation*. 2006;114(16):1687-1692.
13. Agrawal P, Arora S, Singh B, Manamalli A, Dolia PB. Association of macrovascular complications of type 2 diabetes mellitus with serum magnesium levels. *Diabetes Metab Syndr*. 2011;5(1):41-44.
14. Kousa A, Puustinen N, Karvonen M, Moltchanova E. The regional association of rising type 2 diabetes incidence with magnesium in drinking water among young adults. *Environ Res*. 2012; 112:126-128.
15. Kim DJ, Xun P, Liu K, Loria C, Yokota K, Jacobs Jr DR, He K. Magnesium intake in relation to systemic inflammation, insulin resistance, and the incidence of diabetes. *Diabetes care*. 2010 Dec 1;33(12):2604-10.
16. Resnick LM, Gupta RK, Bhargava KK, Hgruenspan H, Alderman MH, Laragh J. Magnesium deficiency in diabetes. *Hypertension*. 1991; 17:951-7.
17. Erasmus RT, Olukoga AO, Alanamu RA, Adewoye HO, Bojuwoye B. Plasma magnesium and retinopathy in black African diabetics. *Tropical and geographical medicine*. 1989 Jul 1;41(3):234-7.
18. Bereda G. Difference between Type 1 And 2 Diabetes Mellitus. *Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences*, 2022; 5(12): 2375–2379.
19. Kao WL, Folsom AR, Nieto FJ, Mo JP, Watson RL, Brancati FL. Serum and dietary magnesium and the risk for type 2 diabetes mellitus: the Atherosclerosis Risk in Communities Study. *Archives of internal medicine*. 1999 Oct 11;159(18):2151-9.
20. Maria C, Trimbake SB, Mhapankar TP, Pratinidhi SA. Magnesium – A Forgotten Cation in Women. *Eur J Biomed Pharm Sci*. 2018;5(3):538– 41.
21. Housecroft CE, Sharpe AG. *Inorganic chemistry*. 3rd ed. Prentice Hall; 2008. p. 305–6.
22. Ash R. *The top 10 of everything 2006- the ultimate book of lists*. DK; 2005.
23. Hoboken NJ. *Van Nostrand's scientific encyclopedia*. New York: Wiley InterScience; 2006.
24. Leroy J. *Necessite du magnesium pour la croissance de la souris*. *Competsrendus Des*. 1926; 94:431–3.
25. Lusk JE, Williams RJP, Kennedy EP. Magnesium and the growth of *Escherichia coli*. *J Biol Chem*. 1968;(10):2618–24.
26. Marschner H. *Mineral nutrition in higher plants*. San Diego: Academic Press; 1995.
27. Wälti MK, Zimmermann MB, Spinass GA, Hurrell RF. Low plasma magnesium in type 2 diabetes. *Swiss Med Wkly*. 2003;133(19-20):289–92.
28. Sales CH, Pedrosa FLD. Magnesium and diabetes mellitus: their relation. *Clin Nutr*. 2006; 25:554–62.
29. Barbagallo M, Dominguez LJ. Magnesium and type 2 diabetes. *World J Diab*. 2015;6 (10): 1152–7.
30. Pham PC, Pham PM, Pham SV, Miller JM, Pham PT. Hypomagnesemia in patients with type 2 diabetes. *Clin J Am Soc Nephrol*. 2007;2(2):366–73.
31. Yossef HM, Ghanem NS, Al-Jarhi UM, Shaker OG. Relation of serum magnesium level to microvascular complications and the components of metabolic syndrome in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *The Egyptian Journal of Internal Medicine*. 2017 Sep;29(3): 100-4.
32. Saeed H, Haj S, Qasim B. Estimation of magnesium level in type 2 diabetes mellitus and its correlation with HbA1c level. *Endocrinology, diabetes & metabolism*. 2019 Jan;2(1):e00048.
33. Aksit M, Aksit MZ, Basok BI. The impact of magnesium on glycemic regulation. *Int J Med Biochem*. 2019;2(1):13-8.
34. Wahid A, Verma GC, Meena CP, Pathan AR. Study of serum magnesium level in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus and its

correlation with glycosylated hemoglobin and diabetic complications. International Journal of Advances in Medicine. 2017 Mar 23;4(2):311.

35. Kumar P, Bhargava S, Agarwal PK, Garg A, Khosla A. Association of serum magnesium

with type 2 diabetes mellitus and diabetic retinopathy. Journal of family medicine and primary care. 2019 May;8(5):1671.